

STRATEGIES FOR INTRODUCING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND MODERN METHODS INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation.

This article provides analytical information on the strategy of introducing digital technologies and modern methods to the educational process in Uzbekistan.

Keywords

Electronic Government, labor market, Finnish education, strategic goal, Individualization of educational processes, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" and "mixed education" technologies.

In accordance with the Presidential Decree on additional measures to introduce the digital economy, electronic government and information systems into the public administration system, the "Electronic Government"¹⁷⁹ system, including the administrative procedures for the provision of public services aimed at simplifying the teeth and improving quality. At the same time, a number of unsolved problems and shortcomings remain that prevent digitization and the transition to a digital economy. In particular, uniform principles of development of state information systems have not been developed, activities in this regard are carried out without interaction with other information systems.

Development of the education system is a strategic goal. It is necessary to improve the quality of training of highly qualified personnel and develop human capital based on the requirements of the labor market for the modernization of the country and sustainable socio-economic development. It is necessary to increase the level of admission to higher education institutions, to train highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking, independent decision-making personnel based on international standards, to create the necessary conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and spiritual development.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁹[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/E-government#:~:text=E-government%20\(short%20for%20electronic,in%20a%20country%20or%20region.](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/E-government#:~:text=E-government%20(short%20for%20electronic,in%20a%20country%20or%20region.)

¹⁸⁰ <https://www.revistaespacios.com/a19v40n09/a19v40n09p15.pdf>

The following measures are being implemented to introduce digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process:¹⁸¹

Country	Finland
Primary languages	Finnish, Swedish, and English
Minister of Education	Jussi Saramago
Minister of Science and Culture	Annika Saarikko
National education budget (2018)	€ 11.9 billion
Population (2018)	5.53 million
Literacy Rate	99%
Primary Enrollment	99.7%
Secondary Enrollment	66.2%
Top Ranking University in Finland	University of Helsinki

¹⁸¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666412722000137>

Now let's talk about foreign experience in the field of education.

According to experts, the best education system in the world is in Finland. Finland is one of the most developed countries in Europe. So, what makes the Finnish education system, considered the best in the world, different from others? There is no such thing as a prestigious or ordinary school in Finland.¹⁸²

All schools are state owned and have the same funding and the same equipment and facilities:

The motto of Finnish schools is: "We prepare the child for life or for the exam." We chose the first one". Therefore, in Finnish schools, the exam is taken only once - when the student turns 16. In Finnish schools, the most important thing is to prepare the student for an independent life. Therefore, they are taught to acquire knowledge independently. Instead of memorized formulas, children learn how to use reference books, calculators, and the Internet. Teachers spend 4 hours a day in class and 2 hours a week on teacher training. In Finland, teaching is a prestigious profession. There is a lot of competition for teaching jobs in higher education. In Finland, general secondary education is free, including free lunches, trips, school buses and parents cannot be charged.

Finnish schools are rightly recognized as the best in the world: 15-minute breaks, nature lessons in all weathers and minimal homework are among them. In addition, the education system is not only free from old traditions, but is becoming one of the best in the world. Finnish teachers often conduct lessons outside the school. Thus, Finns are struggling with the huge gap created between modern children and real life thanks to the virtual world. "Extracurricular impressions have

¹⁸² <https://leverageedu.com/blog/finland-education-system/>

geographical, literary, scientific and historical aspects. All research begins with the Earth, because there is life on it."

Finnish students usually have a 15-minute break after every 45-minute lesson they spend outside with their classmates. This regulation of breathing helps students to concentrate and learn better, while also calming teachers and reducing stress. The Finns realized this long ago and introduced mandatory breaks in schools in the 1960s. In the 1980s, large-scale reforms were implemented in the field of higher education in Finland. Since then, every future teacher becomes a specialist with a master's degree in scientific research.

Ten years later, teachers must develop curricula and teaching methods. Often, principals and principals themselves teach in their schools. There is no clear hierarchy in Finnish schools: most principals teach and manage at the same time. In this way, educational leaders gain first-hand experience of classroom teaching. If teachers are mentored by peers who have faced similar challenges, they will be more receptive to criticism and discuss issues more easily.

Teachers in Switzerland are well paid. Local teachers earn an average of \$68,000 per year, the highest among OECD countries.

In Thailand, 14% of university graduates (slightly more than in other countries) are teachers. But most institutions of higher education are vocational schools, not universities. Less than 20% of university graduates specialize in science and technology. (Over 50% in Singapore).

There are several types of high schools in South Korea: public high schools (administered by the Korean Ministry of Education and Technology, Ministry of Culture, Physical Education, and Tourism), general high schools (administered by higher education institutions in each province), and private high schools.

Higher schools are also divided into several types depending on the subjects taught:

- secondary schools,
- specialized schools (agricultural, industrial, maritime, information),
- special schools (lyceums), technical schools,
- foreign language schools,
- physical education schools,
- art schools.

In the Republic of Korea, there are also higher schools specially established by the Ministry of Education.

They mainly specialize in agriculture, fisheries, industry, and international languages.

It can be analyzed from the above information that both the state and private individuals pay special attention to the education system in developed countries. As a result, students in developed countries learn and learn to work independently with computer technology starting from kindergarten. In our country, this indicator has increased significantly in the last 10 years.

Individualization of educational processes on the basis of digital technologies, distance education services, webinars, online education, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" and "mixed education" technologies are being widely implemented in practice.

Information technologies offer many new forms of education, especially in recent years, the principle of a holistic approach in the modular education system is gaining strength. The adaptation of different forms and methods led to the introduction of mixed education as a novelty. As Declan Burn said about "blended education" - "this education is aimed at the effective use of rich pedagogical experience." Such an approach can be based on the use of different methods of information presentation, traditional activities in the organization of training and educational process, information technology, individually and in groups.

Such a colorful approach does not tire the student and increases his enthusiasm for studying. The main task is to ensure the compatibility of the selected methods and to achieve high efficiency at a low cost.

For several years now, among advanced teachers, a new method - "Flipped class" or the alternate class method - has been widely used. This is one of their blended learning models. At home, students learn theory, and in the classroom, they practice practical skills and ask the teacher questions.

Usually the teacher lectures in the school, in the class, leaving very little time for questions and exercises. How to put all this into practice, you often have to figure it out yourself at home. Teaching takes place in the classroom and many students find it difficult to fully absorb the material. Most teachers spend their time explaining material and imparting knowledge, and less time teaching how to analyze, evaluate, and create something. Jonathan Bergman, one of the founders of the idea of the "flipped classroom", explains that the "flipped model" of learning aims to transfer knowledge to the personal space of the student and spend more time on practical skills.

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